

NANOPAPER ENABLED SHAPE-MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITE FOR ELECTRICAL ACTUATION

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1 General Introduction

Shape-memory polymers (SMPs) are able to recover their original shape upon exposure to an external stimulus. The shape-memory phenomenon in SMPs arises from a dual segment system, in which one segment is highly elastic and the other is able to remarkably reduce its stiffness in the presence of a particular stimulus. SMPs have a far higher recoverable strain (up to 400%), much lower density, more convenient processing and fabrication techniques, and properties that are more easily tailored to better accommodate the requirements of a particular application than the shape-memory alloys (SMAs). In addition to these advantages, low cost—not only for the materials themselves but also in processing and fabrication—enables the use of SMPs for a wide range of applications. In this article, synthesis of two novel thermosetting SMP, fiber reinforced SMP composites (SMPCs) and their electrical activation, as well as the applications of SMPCs are discussed.

2 SMP Composite Coated with Nanopaper

Conductive CNT and CNF nanopapers are primarily introduced for the actuation of shape recovery of an SMP by electrically resistive Joule heating.[1,2] The carbon nanopaper was manufactured using a traditional pressure vacuum deposition process. The generally accepted method of making carbon nanopaper involves the use of non-ionic surfactants, which aids the CNTs or CNFs dispersion into the aqueous or organic solvent. The suspension needed to be sonicated for a sufficient amount of time at room temperature, and then suspension was filtered through a hydrophilic or hydrophobic membrane filter with the aid of pressure to form nanopaper. The suspensions were membrane filtered under positive pressure to yield uniform films. The carbon individual was bonded by Van der Waals forces.

After filtration, the remaining water and surfactants in the nanopaper was dried in an oven at 120°C for 2h. The nanopapers were found to be porous, with the pore size determined by the weight concentration of the carbon individual. The nanopaper has a porous structure with the individuals entangled with each other. No large aggregates were found, indicating a uniform distribution and close packing in the nanopaper. A network structure was formed by the molecular interactions and mechanical interlocking between nanotubes or nanofibers. Such a continuous network made of individual nanotubes or nanofibers acts as a conductive path for electrons, making the nanopapers electrically conductive. Since CNTs and CNFs are two of the most electrically conductive materials known, nanopaper is considered one of the best candidates for a conductive material that would allow an insulating polymer to behave like a conductor. This, in turn, could lead to even greater advances in enabling these continuous networks to act as conductive paths. The electrical resistivity of the nanopaper enabled SMP composite was measured with the four-point probe method. The electrical resistivity of the SMP composites coated with different weight fractions of nanopapers was different from each other. For example, the SMP composites were coated with one layer of carbon nanopaper containing (either) 0.6, 1.2, 1.8 or 2.4g of CNTs (or CNFs). As the weight of each nanopaper increased, the average electrical resistivity of the composite sample regularly decreased from 4.877 to 0.937 Ωcm (while 5.268 decreased to 1.544 Ωcm for those coated with CNF nanopaper). The more carbon individuals present, the more conductive paths were formed in the nanopaper. Given more conductive paths in one bulk, more electrons are involved in an electrical circuit. Therefore, the electrical current amplitude and current-carrying capability increase.

The thicknesses of the four composite samples with various weight concentrations of nanopaper were kept constant. And the function and effectiveness of the nanopaper in the actuation of SMP composites by electrically resistive Joule heating were experimentally demonstrated. Figure 1 shows the recovery of the SMP composite coated with 1.2g CNT nanopaper as a proper electric current was applied. The shape recovery process of the flat (permanent shape) composite specimen with a dimension of 100×6×3 mm was demonstrated.

Fig. 1. Series of photographs showing the macroscopic shape-memory effect of an SMP composite integrated with 1.2 g of CNT nanopaper.[1] ©Copyright 2008, Wiley-Vch Verlag GmbH & Co.

3 SMP Composite Incorporated with Nanopaper and Magnetic Alignment

The synergistic effect of self-assembled carbon nanopaper and vertical alignments on the SMP composite was further studied to mitigate the negative effect of randomly dispersed CNFs on the recovery ratio. The combination of nanopaper and magnetic alignment was thus employed to improve both electrical and thermal conductivities of the SMP. The conductive nanopaper was used to improve the electrical property by coating on the surface of the SMP composite, to enable the shape recovery induced by electricity. Electromagnetic fillers were then blended with, and vertically aligned into the SMP resin in a magnetic field, to facilitate the heat transfer from the nanopaper to the underlying SMP part and effectively accelerate the electro-active recovery performance.[3,4] The vertical alignments directs the electric current to pass through the insulating polymer, and transfer the electric power into resistive heating power.

In the previous experiment, it has been demonstrated that the electrical and thermal conductivities of the SMP have been significantly improved by the blended conductive CNFs. However, the recovery ratio of the tested SMP composites was slightly

decreased by the randomly dispersed conductive fillers in the recovery process. Here, electromagnetic nickel nanostrand and CNTs were respectively blended with, and vertically aligned within the SMP resin on a magnetic field to facilitate heat transfer.

The SMP composite blended with 8 wt.% vertically aligned nickel nanostrands was further utilized to demonstrate the electrically triggered actuation. Experimentally, the recovery process was characterized using a modified bending test method. The flat SMP composite was initially bent in a “U”-like shape at a proper temperature. This temporary shape was retained until the specimen was cooled back down to room temperature. No apparent recovery was found after being kept in the air for 2 h. Figure 2 presents the recovery of the SMP composite from a fixed bent shape to its originally straight shape under a constant voltage.

Fig. 2. Electrically resistive heating-induced SME of SMP/nanopaper nanocomposites with 8 wt% vertically aligned nickel nanostrands,[3] ©Copyright 2011, RSC Publishing.

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